

Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business content

D2.3 version 3.0

December 2018

The logo for MERLIN, featuring a small red square to the left of the word "merlin" in a lowercase, sans-serif font.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780.460

Copyright © MERLIN Consortium
<https://merlin-ict.eu>

MERLIN

Methodologies for Researcher
Led INnovations

GA No. 780.460

ICT-32-2017 EU H2020

MERLIN

Methodologies for Researcher Led Innovations

Nº780.460. ICT-32-2017. EU H2020

Confidentiality Level: PU

Document Type	Contract Deliverable	
Document & WP No.	D2.3	WP2
Document Title	Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business content	
Release date	Version 3.0 – 14/12/2018	

Executive summary

This document, D2.3 – Entrepreneurial mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business up content – is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020".

Merlin aims to foster and accelerate the transfer of knowledge from the projects funded in FP7 and H2020, be it on the form of license agreement, patent or ideally, spinoff or startup to directly exploit them, by organising practical hands-on workshops; meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors; and by attending scientific conferences to reach a wider public. The programme will equip participants with knowledge, skills and a network to generate market-led business models to unlock potential and accelerate this journey.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide the content of the 4th and 8th workshops – Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business that will be used by all the members of the Consortium when conducting the workshops at their locations.

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 780.460

Copyright © MERLIN Consortium
<https://merlin-ict.eu>

Document Control Page

Title	Entrepreneurial Mindset content		
Creator	St John's Innovation Centre		
Description	Description of the content used in the fourth and eight workshops – Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business.		
Review status	Action	Person/Partner	Date
	Completed by WP Leader	Kirsten Masson	
	Approved by Peer Panel		
	Approved by QA	Diego Alonso	
Distribution	Confidential		CO

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	01/09/2018	Kirsten Masson	First version of the deliverable.
2.0	05/12/2018	Alex Cleland	Second Version of Deliverable
3.0	14/12/2018	Alex Cleland & Kirsten Masson	Final version of deliverable

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Audience	5
1.2. Structure	6
2. Workshop Entrepreneurial Mindset.....	7
2.1. General information about the workshop	7
2.2. Introduction to the workshop	7
2.3. Introduction to Entrepreneurship	11
2.4. Effectuation	16
2.5. Goal Setting	23
2.6. Networking & Partnerships	32
2.7. Conclusions and homework	38
2.8. Assess your aptitude.....	39
3. Building the Right IP For Your Business	40
3.1. General information about the workshop	40
3.2. Introduction to the workshop	41
3.3. Difference between Start-ups and Spin-offs	42
3.4. Intellectual property- IP.....	50
3.5. Working within university and other regulations & Creating Sustainable partnerships	67
3.6. Round table Q&A.....	77
3.7. Conclusions and homework	78
4. Conclusions	79

1. Introduction

This deliverable (D2.3) — Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business content — is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460 and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020"¹ and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020"². The purpose of this document is to provide a description of the material that will be used in the fourth and eighth workshops. All members of the Consortium will use the same content for conducting the workshops at their locations.

Funding in the ICT project under FP7 and H2020 totals over 11.000 million € by the end of the current work programme. Stimulated and supported by these programs, many researchers in universities, institutes and SMEs have worked hard on developing new ground-breaking technologies and disruptive services. But when it comes to commercialize the results or create a company, these researchers are unsure on how to proceed. MERLIN project, funded in the context of the EC initiative *Innovation Radar*, wants to start changing this situation by organizing a set of activities aiming:

- To stimulate a greater interest in the scientific community to view their research results as potential opportunities to be exploited with the correct business model.
- To equip researchers with modern, need-first and market-led methodologies that will help them to shape their ideas and outputs into innovations to be ready for market validation and posterior commercialization.
- To introduce the rich European entrepreneurship ecosystem and the opportunities it offers to create and support startups on their journey.

Among the planned activities, it is worth highlighting the following:

- Organisation of 45 practical workshops covering state-of-the-art innovation and entrepreneurship methodologies in 8 European cities.
- Organisation of 5 workshops in scientific conferences to reach more researchers and engage them with the activities organized by MERLIN and other ICT-32 projects.
- Organisation of 8 meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors by the end of each year.
- Organisation of 4 webinars on SME growth and new business models for public-private partnership.

The document provides the description of the content used for the Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business workshops. It describes the theory to be presented during the workshops as well as the practical exercises which are used to put the theory to the test and ensure the participants develop the practical skills of applying the theory to their own ideas.

1.1. Audience

The main intended audience for this document is the MERLIN project consortium and the European Commission, but also workshop attendees and general public.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/sites/horizon2020/files/FactSheet_Open_Access.pdf

The target audience of the workshops are researchers and startups from the ICT field.

1.2. Structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 presents the content of the Entrepreneurial Mindset workshop.
- Section 3 presents the content of the Building the Right IP For Your Business workshop
- Section 4 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Workshop Entrepreneurial Mindset

2.1. General information about the workshop

Name of the workshop: Entrepreneurial Mindset

Name of the partner which is responsible for the content delivery: St John's Innovation Centre

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results and very early stage SMEs.

Target group needs identified: Don't have the skills to commercialise their research findings and/or ideas, lack the experience in commercial environments for time prioritization and goal setting, they need to challenge their thinking style to become more entrepreneurial.

Key skills to be acquired: More flexible thinking, tools to help e.g. effectuation and goal setting, improved planning and an overall understanding that anyone can be an entrepreneur, time prioritization/time management tools.

The main goals of the workshop:

- Aware of techniques like effectuating[†] to approach decision making in uncertainty
- Equipped with tools to develop realistic short and medium-term goals and to adapt for change
- Ability to foster new partnerships and exploit new opportunities rapidly

Learning methods to be applied: Effectuation, SMART goals, Cantillon, Kirzner, Knight and Schumpeter.

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, able to seat 20-30 people

Requirements for supplies needed: Pens, markers, large sheets of paper, stopwatch or a phone with stopwatch, Flipchart, Coffee, tea, sweets, snacks for break, whiteboard (for reflection) *, Name the entrepreneur answer sheets and printed slides **, effectuation exercise worksheets **, smart goal template sheet **.

* - Not necessary if using Slido software

** - Worksheet provided by St John's Innovation Centre via Google Drive

2.2. Introduction to the workshop

The participants are first introduced first to the **workshop agenda**, which splits the Entrepreneurial Mindset methodology into clear areas;

Then they are introduced to the learning objectives for the Entrepreneurial Mindset workshop (as outlined in the grant agreement):

- Aware of techniques like effectuating to approach decision making in uncertainty
- Equipped with tools to develop realistic short and medium-term goals and to adapt for change

-
- Ability to foster new partnerships and exploit new opportunities rapidly

The trainer will then introduce the rules/guidelines for the workshop, which include:

- No question is a silly question;
- What is said in the room stays in the room;
- Support and challenge each other.

The main purpose of the introduction of the rules for the workshop is to encourage the participants to ask questions, to reassure them that the questions asked will stay in the room, that information they share about their business/idea will stay in the room and everyone should support and challenge each other.

The general information about the workshop is provided:

- General housekeeping (toilets, fire-exits, food and drink)
- Length of the workshop (4 hours);
- Coffee break (20 minutes);
- Slides will be shared with the participants after the workshop- they are available via slide share.

The MERLIN project is presented briefly, introducing the goals of the project, events (other Workshops, webinars, international conferences to be planned). Furthermore, the main information about the Consortium partners is provided. This information is previously detailed in section 1. Introduction.

To encourage collaboration and an atmosphere where participants can contribute, a game of '**Name the entrepreneurs**' will be played. They will be split into groups of around 4 (groups on their tables), and will be given printed out picture sheets, answer sheet to be completed. The participants will introduce themselves with one sentence and will name the entrepreneurs and complete as much of the answer sheet as possible. They will then be asked to pick one entrepreneur from the sheet and consider what qualities the entrepreneur has that they admire. They will be given 15 minutes to complete this task, and then 15 minutes to feedback to the group. The responses of what they admire should be flip charted for reflection in later exercises. This Icebreaker is expected to last last 30 minutes.

The icebreaker is designed to allow participants to look at examples of different people who are entrepreneur's, and to already prompt thoughts about what makes these people entrepreneur's- leading into the focus of the workshop as entrepreneurial mindset. The purpose of the task is to prompt this thought into what makes an entrepreneur and get everybody interacting as a group and with the trainers.

Please note that it has been agreed with consortium partners that they can change the entrepreneur's provided to be more localised to increase engagement from the audience.

The following sections of the document describe the content of each part in detail.

Name the entrepreneurs

Introduce yourself

Name the entrepreneurs

Discuss in your group who is the entrepreneur you admire the most and why?

15 minutes and then feedback to the group

Ice Breaker - Name the entrepreneur

1. Branson- Founder of Virgin group which controls more than 400 companies. \$5bn
2. Muhammad Yunus- Bangladeshi social entrepreneur, banker, pioneering the concepts of microcredit and microfinance. These loans are given to entrepreneurs too poor to qualify for traditional bank loans. The Grameen Bank and Yunus were jointly awarded the Nobel Peace Prize. Co-founder of YSB- YSB creates and empowers social businesses to address and solve social problems around the world. As the international implementation arm for Yunus' vision of a new, humane capitalism, YSB manages incubator funds for social

businesses in developing countries and provides advisory services to companies, governments, foundations and NGOs.

3. Cher Wang- Taiwanese entrepreneur- Co-founder and chairperson of HTC Corporation and integrated chipset maker VIA technologies. Considered one of the most powerful and successful women in technology.

4. Jeff Bezos- Founder, chairman and CEO of Amazon- the world's online largest retailer. Worked on wall street for 8 years before founding amazon on a cross-country road trip from new York city to Seattle. It started as a book store.

5. Diane Von Furstenberg- Begun designing clothes in 1970 with 30k, has risen to the top of the industry and president of the trade association of the country's top 350 designers. She is well known for her wrap dress. Her fashion company is available in over 70 countries and 45 free-standing shops worldwide.

6. Bill Gates- Co-founder of Microsoft, which has become the world's largest software business through tech innovation, business strategy and aggressive business tactics. He took existing technology and applied it to a specific market and then dominated this area.

7. Kylie Jenner- World's youngest self-made billionaire, media star who founded her own cosmetics business. Part of Kardashian family.

8. Oprah- She launched her own tv show- the Oprah Winfrey show. She gained ownership of the program from ABC bringing it under her own company 'Harpo productions'. During the 1990s, Oprah expanded her business into many areas besides the television. She entered various fields such as publishing, music, film, health and fitness and education. In 1994, Oprah's initiatives for the protection of children against abuse were rewarded when the then US President, Bill Clinton signed the 'Oprah Bill,' a new law designed to protect children against abuse.

9. Zuckerbeg- American technology entrepreneur and philanthropist best known for co-founding and leading Facebook as its chairman and CEO. Famously launched facebook from his dormitory room in Harvard– net worth \$66.4bn

10. Elon Musk- South-African-born business agnate, investor and engineer. Founder, CEO and elad designer at SpaceX, co-founder + CEO of Tesla, Co-founder and CEO of neralink. Net worth \$20.8bn. He dropped out of a PhD at Stanford after 2 days ad founded Zip2 which he eventually sold for \$340bn. Then founded X.com which went onto become paypal which was bought by Ebay for \$1.5bn.

2.3. Introduction to Entrepreneurship

Definition of an entrepreneur

A person who sets up a business taking on financial risks in the hope of profit.

NOT a job

10

Slide 10- Defining and entrepreneur will begin to guide the workshop to what an entrepreneur is, leading into the role of an entrepreneur. This content has been created using 4 theorists- Cantillon, Kirzner, Knight and Schumpeter.

Cantillon, writing in the 18th century was the first to recognise the crucial role of the entrepreneur as a catalyst for economic changes and development. He was the originator for the term 'entrepreneur' as someone who organises and assumes the risk of business in return for profit. He recognised 3 economic categories- entrepreneur's, landowners and workers- positioning entrepreneur's as a central economic actor for change. Schumpeter looked at entrepreneur's as innovators and found they bring about change through the introduction of new technologies processes and products.

Knights found entrepreneur's as risk takers, when a person is prepared to take risks in parallel with high levels of personal responsibility, the entrepreneur takes responsibility for their calculated risk.

Kirzner said an entrepreneur is someone who spot opportunity, they are alert to situations which they are able to commercialise due to additional understanding of the market.

These 4 early theorists categorised different areas that we identify as entrepreneurship- economic actor for change through risk taking, innovation and taking responsibility (internal locus of control). These are now key factors in what is recognised as an entrepreneur.

Types of entrepreneurs

- Accidental
- Reluctant
- Serial

- Pushed
- Pulled
- Driven

What is the motivation?

11

Slide 11 details different types of entrepreneur's and how they're driven with examples. As with guess the entrepreneur the examples provided can be changes to be more appropriate for workshop participants. The 3 types of entrepreneur's detailed are accidental, reluctant and serial, with the motivations being pushed, pulled and driven.

Accidental- Arash Ferdowski Dropbox- To secure funding for his cloud storage business, Drew Houston, original founder of Dropbox was told by his potential investor that he wouldn't be funded unless he had a business partner. For various reasons none of his friends were able to join the business. So, he had just two weeks to find a complete stranger to become his co-founder. He persuaded a 22-year-old student- Arash Ferdowski to join him. Arash dropped out of college a week later to join Dropbox not knowing what he was signing up for. They secured the investment and the company was launched. Ferdowski's net worth is now \$1.3bn.

Reluctant- Michelle Mone- Founder of **Ultimo**, Baroness Mone is one of the UKs most influential entrepreneurs. She started as a marketer for Canadian beer. She was made redundant from this role and out of necessity started her own business, Ultimo, which created better-fitting bras. She now has an estimated net worth of £60m.

Reluctant and Accidental- John Pemberton – John Pemberton was wounded in the American Civil War. Pemberton owned a drug store in Georgia. There he developed his French Wine Coca nerve tonic, which was meant to be a substitute for morphine, the drug he had originally taken to treat pain from his war injuries.

He later changed the recipe to a non-alcoholic version after his county passed prohibition legislation. This non-alcoholic version is what eventually became **Coca-Cola**.

Accidental Roxanne Quimby and Burt Shavitz- Burt's Bees started with some extra beeswax from co-founder Shavitz's honey business. The duo created products from that beeswax and started their company with just \$200 they made at a junior high school craft fair. Within a year, they had made more than \$20,000 and their products are now sold worldwide. The company is worth over \$1B.

Serial- James Dyson- Dyson first invented a wheelbarrow with a single round wheel- this was later combined to his bagless vacuum cleaner which used cyclone technology he invented. This took no less than 5,127 tweaks and modifications between 1979 - 1984. His wife's income kept the family afloat as his idea was initially rejected by British retailers. His perseverance paid off with the Dyson brand becoming synonymous with innovation and excellence. The cyclone technology has since been used for other products including hand dryers, fans and hairdryers.

There can be different drivers for entrepreneurs;

Pushed- Unemployment, job insecurity, poverty, disagreement with management, does not "fit in" with organisation, no other alternative – Michelle Mone

Pulled- Independence, need for achievement, recognition, personal development, personal wealth – Burts Bees, James Dyson

Driven- Driven by the next idea, entrepreneur's that are always searching for the next idea-Richard Branson, Oprah Winfrey, James Dyson

Several drivers may be influencing at the same time – ie the need to be driven and have autonomy links to the Pull driver.

Characteristics of an entrepreneur

Cantillon – First recognised the role of an entrepreneur 'one who takes between' Catalyst for economic change – Cantillon

Knight – Calculated risk taker

Kirzner – Ability to spot opportunity - Entrepreneurs key ability is 'creative' alertness

Schumpeter – Innovator - Creative disruption

12

Slide 12 summarises those points and looks at some other considerations for an entrepreneurial personality. This is based upon the 2 leading theorists- McClelland (1984) and Meredith et al. (1997). The points that there cover differ slightly but are all traits are recognised and entrepreneurial.

Discussion - Mindset

What do entrepreneurs have in common?

Are these fixed traits, or can they change throughout your life? If so... how?

What does success look like for an entrepreneur?

13

Slide 13: Discussion Mindset- discussion. 3 questions will be posed to the group to be discussed in their same small groups;

- What do entrepreneurs have in common?

-
- Are these fixed traits, or can they change throughout your life? If so... how?
 - What does success look like for an entrepreneur?

This exercise in 30 minutes total, 15 minutes discussion in groups to cover each of the questions and 15 minutes feedback group. The answers to these questions will then be flip charted and then categorised into broader areas. Points that we want to extract from the group are;

- Locus of control. Locus of control is an individual's belief system regarding the causes of his or her experiences and the factors to which that person attributes success or failure. If a person has an internal locus of control, that person attributes success to his or her own efforts and abilities. A person who expects to succeed will be more motivated and more likely to learn. A person with an external locus of control, who attributes his or her success to luck, fate or controlled by others, will be less likely to make the effort needed to learn
- This theory is important for entrepreneurs because believing in one's own active influence helps to increase the motivation to reach success
- Innovative/creative – thinkers outside of the box, willing to experiment/try new things
- Autonomy Need to be in control and avoid the restrictions and rules of established organization Or Non-conformist Someone who does not fit in with their existing employment. The non-conformist behaviour may trigger them to start their own business in preference to conforming to the regulations of the existing business
- Ability to adapt to change - Thrives in uncertainty, likes new things, can think on their feet
- Need for Achievement - High achievers are those that accept responsibility for decisions and for achieving solutions to problems. Very often satisfaction is gained from finding the solutions to a problem rather than with the monetary reward.
- Owners with a high need for achievement prefer moderately challenging tasks rather than routine or very difficult tasks. They take personal responsibility for their performance, seek feedback and search for new and better ways to improve their performance. High need for achievement is correlated with business success.
- Self-Efficacy is the belief of performing a task effectively. People with high self-efficacy are likely to persevere when problems arise and take actions to resolve. They also show a higher degree of personal initiative and actively searching for information.

This should bring out whether entrepreneurship traits are inherent or can be learnt, with the trainers able to direct the conversation to how can you change your mindset to be more entrepreneurial? This is ideally shaped as an opportunity to learn entrepreneurial skills- easier for some than others but there is always room for personal development and to improve.

The group will be asked if they have been able to make their mindset more entrepreneurial, any training that has worked for them. Suggest that mentors, practise, moving away from comfort zones, learning from others are all good ways to adapt and make changes to a mindset.

The last question is to ask what success looks like- it is not always about money – it is likely more about recognition, being remembered for something, making a difference to the world. What does success look like for the participants in the workshop.

This question is based around 2 leading theorists who have been at the forefront of identifying entrepreneurial personality.

McClelland D.C. (1984); Need for achievement, Calculated risk taker, High internal locus of control, Creativity, Innovative, need for autonomy, Tolerance for ambiguity, Vision, Self-efficacy **Meredith et al (1997)**; Self-confident, Risk taking, Flexible, need for achievement, Strong desire to be independent

Calculated **risk taking: (Knight)**

Risk tolerance individuals are more likely to start a business than risk averse people. Linked to need for achievement as need for achievement leads to moderate risk taking.

Appetite for risk varies amongst individuals and therefore difficult to calibrate.

2.4. Effectuation

Begins with the following video (Slide 14), to talk them through the background and principles of effectuation- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TIXVe4nEDEE>.

How do you go about tackling problems?

Causation...

I've got a problem, there's a solution, that's my answer

...Effectuation

Begins with who you are, what can I do, what are your own skills and competencies, thinking beyond work

15

2 thinking styles are introduced- Causal thinking and effectual thinking. They are two different, innate styles of thought that are particularly applicable to business owners. Causal thinkers start with a goal, and they take stock of the materials and means available to them, and then develop and carry out a step-by-step plan to achieve that goal.

Effectual thinkers work more fluidly, beginning with what they have at present, such as ideas, personal strengths and materials at hand, and then work by combining the elements available to them and adjusting their plans as they progress. Effectual thinkers don't begin with clearly-defined goal; rather, they allow the goal to emerge organically out of the process. Causal thinking, which is taught in business schools and other disciplines, is familiar to most of us. Effectual thinking, on the other hand, defines the realm of the entrepreneur.

The distinction between causal and effectual thinking originated in 2001 with the work of Dr. Saras D. Sarasvathy, who interviewed 27 top business executives and entrepreneurs to find out how they would approach solving business problems. She found that the majority of the entrepreneurs employed a style of thinking that was the inverse of the more traditional, causal thinking style taught in business schools. Dr. Sarasvathy used the term "effectual" to describe the approach used by the entrepreneurs in her studies.

Effectual thinking is a set of heuristics. A heuristic is a mental shortcut that helps us to make decisions and judgements quickly without having to spend time researching and analysing information. Heuristics enable a person to discover and learn something for themselves, it is defined by the Oxford dictionary as 'a *'hands-on' or interactive heuristic approach to learning'*. Heuristics has not been put into a slide to keep the content digestible across Europe and to better cater and interest the target audience and workshop groups.

Entrepreneurs typically must operate in highly ambiguous and uncertain environments in the pursuit of a new venture. Using heuristics to piece together limited information to make convincing decision may be the only way to move forward the business opportunity. In practical terms, the window of opportunity may close by the time enough information becomes available for the factual decision maker to decide meaning that they must make decisions based on less than an ideal amount of information.

Effectuation principles

1. Bird in the Hand

2. Affordable Loss

Effectuation principles cont.

3. Lemonade

4. Crazy/ Patchwork Quilt

Effectuation principles cont.

5. Pilot on the Plane

Slides 16-18 will then talk through the 5 Effectuation principles;

1. Bird-in-hand {start with your means}; Work with what you have. (Kirzner) start with your means. Know who you are, what you know, and who you know – rather than spend energy on defining and refining pre-set goals. When expert entrepreneurs set out to build a new venture, they start with their means: who I am, what I know, and whom I know. Then, the entrepreneurs imagine possibilities that originate from their means. Contrasts with pre-set goals or opportunities; Causal reasoning works inversely by assembling means after a goal is set.
2. Affordable Loss {focus on the downside risk}; Invest only as much as you can afford to lose, and let your partners invest only as much as they can afford to lose – rather than describing expected returns. Expert entrepreneurs limit risk by understanding what they can afford to lose at each step, instead of seeking large all-or nothing opportunities. They choose goals and actions where there is upside even if the downside ends up happening. Contrasts with expected return; Causal reasoning first targets a return, then works to minimize associated risk.
3. Lemonade {leverage contingencies}; Embrace and leverage surprises – rather than avoiding them. Expert entrepreneurs invite the surprise factor. Instead of making “what-if” scenarios to deal with worst-case scenarios, experts interpret “bad” news and surprises as potential clues to create new markets. Contrasts with avoiding surprises; Causal reasoning works to minimize the probability of unexpected outcomes.
4. Crazy/Patchwork-Quilt; Form partnerships and build networks. Talk to potential customers and partners and build a network of self-selected stakeholders who will jointly commit to the partnership. Expert entrepreneurs build partnerships with self-selecting stakeholders. By obtaining pre-

commitments from these key partners early on in the venture, experts reduce uncertainty and co-create the new market with its interested participants. Contrasts with Competitive analysis; Causal reasoning presumes that competitors are rivals to contend with.

5. Pilot in the Plane {control v. predict}; Co-create the future. Build products and services together – rather than reacting to inevitable trends. By focusing on activities within their control, expert entrepreneurs know their actions will result in the desired outcomes. An effectual worldview is rooted in the belief that the future is neither found nor predicted, but rather made. Contrasts with inevitable trends; Causal reasoning accepts that established market forces will cause the future to unfold.

This will be followed by the Effectuation model on Slide 19 which shows how the principles fit into the model. The effectuation model continually re-iterates as you move through the process, this leads to new goals and new means, giving the possibilities of new product, markets etc. The aim is to continually work through the effectuation loop to drive forward new opportunities.

Effectuation model

Effectuation considerations

- Causality and effectuation are both cognitive methodologies and they can exist in parallel
- Does not cover business planning and design thinking
- Effectuation is not a theory of "anything goes" – it is a theory of constrained creativity
- Effectuation is not just for small, start-up firms – it can be applied to large firms and economies as well

With any mode there are considerations and weaknesses to be explored. For the effectuation model these are outlined in slide 20. These are that effectuation and causation are used in parallel- businesses typically use both. Take Dyson for example- he started with the bagless vacuum to solve a problem (starting with his idea)- but used his means- cyclone technology he had developed- to innovate the product. This has led to his further innovations.

One method is not necessarily better than another and one method might work better for a personality type than another.

This section will finish with an effectuation exercise to reinforce the learning of the slides. The activity is designed to help participants to understand the model and put it into practise. The exercise will be run in small groups (tables or up to 5).

The exercise will have the group to agree an idea for a food related business – they are encouraged to be as creative as they want to be. 2 worksheets will be provided for this exercise. The exercise will run as follows;

1. The group will agree an idea for a food related business – to be as creative as they can be. Work through the 2 worksheets provided.
2. Sheet 1
 - a. Your idea – describe in one sentence
 - b. Means from the group members which might be relevant
 - c. Affordable loss: Agree how much the group could invest into the business and afford to lose (e.g. time, money, etc.)

- d. How useful are your means in relation to your idea? Rate them 1-5
- e. **How could you change your idea to make better use of your means?**

3. Sheet 2

- a. Can you make better use of your means by tweaking your idea?
- b. Go through the effectuation cycle again- by using the questions outlined on sheet 2 and see what differences in approach to idea and affordable loss become apparent.

This exercise is expected to last between 20 – 30 minutes. After the groups have worked through the exercises each group will be given 2 minutes to feedback on their idea (Slide 23), their means and any changes made using the effectuation cycle.

This has been chosen as it a universal business type/sector that anyone can have thoughts on and interact with. This allows for everyone to be able to contribute to the task and to better understand the effectuation cycle.

Effectuation exercise

Think about an idea for a **FOOD RELATED** business your group could set-up using the effectuation methodology

What is your idea, relevant means, how much can you afford to lose?

Effectuate your idea

How could you change your idea to make better use of your means?

Effectuation Cycle

Further develop and adapt the business idea...

22

Feedback to the group

Each team to feedback to the group in 2 minutes max

Explain the idea and how it developed through the effectuation model.

23

At this point participants will have a coffee break to break up the workshop (slide 24- approximately 20 mins).

2.5. Goal Setting

The topic will be introduced as goal setting being a way of thinking- Successful people develop the habits of personal strategic planning. They make a list of exactly what they want to accomplish in the short, medium,

and long term. Once you develop the habit of setting goals and making plans to accomplish them, it will become a natural process for you. This is the introduction to the topic of Goal Setting to a way of thinking.

Goal setting is a powerful tool for motivation- and keeping motivated for the long and short term.

Locke and Latham late 1960s performed much of the research that informs goal theory. This is the theory behind much of goal setting and has informed slide 26. They came up with 5 principles of goal setting;

1. Clarity – set clear and precise goals
2. Challenging – careful balance to set the right degree of challenge
3. Commitment – rational as well as emotional – team setting always helpful if the team have some say in the goals that are being set to help engagement
4. Feedback - check in regularly
5. Task complexity – highly complex goals can be overwhelming – need sufficient time to work towards the goal, improve performance, practice, learn what is necessary for success. Lack of accomplishment of goals leads to dissatisfaction – need to get the level of challenge and complexity just right

OKRs – Objectives and Key Results – goal setting framework

Goal setting- a way of thinking

A good goal is like a strenuous exercise, it makes you stretch

Building a business without goal setting is like setting out on a journey with no starting point or arrival time frame. **Business goal setting is one of the big differences between successful entrepreneurs** and entrepreneurs that seem to be going nowhere.

A good example of goal setting is New year's resolutions (Slide 27). The presenter will pose the question of how many people made a new year's resolution, and then how many people kept it. Citing that *USA Today* reported on a study of people who had set New Year's resolutions. They found that only 4% of the people who had made New Year's resolutions, but had not put them in writing, had followed through on them. 46% of those people who had written down their New Year's resolutions followed them through. It makes the point that not only making a goal but writing it down will help a person to stick to it. Further to this, a recent report quoted entrepreneurs who received advice from peers with an active approach to managing people— instituting regular meetings, setting goals consistently, and providing frequent feedback to employees—grew 28% larger and were 10 percentage points less likely to fail.

Goal setting example

SMART goal setting is a goal setting guideline that helps people to set goals that they will be able to sit to. To link this to Locke & Latham's research into the goal setting paradox we know that they should be setting goals that are performance outcome and process oriented. Meaning they cover all time ranges (short, medium and long) as well as the process, individual day-to-day goals, performance, how they go about achieving the goals, and outcome goals, what the final sought after outcome is. The combination of all of these goals is designed to increase a person's motivation toward a task so that they are more likely to be successful.

Make these goals SMART

2 new years resolutions;

Diet related- I aim to eat better this year

Exercise related- I will exercise more this year

28

The SMART goals exercise (Slide 28) is to make 2 generic new year's resolution goals SMART. Goals should be SMART: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic/Relevant, Time Bound.

Ask the group to suggest good Smart goals for the weak goals that are on the slides New year's resolutions- Diet related; I aim to eat better this year

Fitness related; I will exercise more this year

How can participants change these goals to make them SMART goals? Shout out ideas and provide the SMART goals worksheet which details the following prompts-

Specific: What is the desired result? (who, what, when, why, how)

Measurable: How can you quantify (numerically or descriptively) completion? How can you measure progress?

Achievable: What skills are needed? What resources are necessary? How does environment impact goal achievement? Does the goal require the right amount of effort?

Relevant: Is the goal in alignment with the overall mission or strategy?

Time Bound: What is the deadline? Is the deadline realistic?

A worksheet has been created for participants to record goals relevant to how they are taking their research/early stage business forward in the next 12 months.

Any plan is better than no plan at all

- **Step 1:** Write your goals down.
- **Step 2:** Set a deadline for achieving the goal.
- **Step 3:** Make a list of everything to be done to achieve the goal.
- **Step 4:** Organize your list of action steps into a plan based on priorities and sequence

Ref: Brian Tracey Million Dollar Habits

Any plan is better than no plan at all cont.

- **Step 5:** Identify the obstacles or limitations that might hold you back from achieving your goal
- **Step 6:** Take Action
- **Step 7:** Make it a Habit

Ref: Brian Tracey Million Dollar Habits

Within this area is planning (Slides 29-30). Participants will be asked to consider why planning is important, and the trainers can help to tie to goal setting is the attendees do not. This helps transition to slide 30: Any plan is better than not plan at all.

This will guide participants through the following steps;

1. **Step 1:** Write your goals down. Make them measurable and specific.
2. **Step 2:** Set a deadline for achieving the goal. If it's a large goal, break it down into smaller parts and set sub - deadlines.

3. **Step 3:** Make a list of everything to be done to achieve the goal. As you think of new items, add them to your list until it's complete.
4. **Step 4:** Organize your list of action steps into a plan based on priorities and sequence.
 - a. In organizing by **priorities**, you determine the most important things you can possibly do on your list to achieve your goal. The 80/20 rule applies: 20 percent of the things you do will account for 80 percent of your results. If you don't set clear priorities, you'll spend much of your time on small and irrelevant tasks that don't help you achieve your goal.
 - b. In organizing by **sequence**, you determine what must be done before something else can be done. You create a checklist. There are always activities that are dependent other activities being completed in advance. What are they, and what is the logical order or sequence of completion?
5. **Step 5:** Identify the obstacles or limitations that might hold you back from achieving your goal, both in the situation and within yourself. "Why have I not achieved this goal already?"
 - a. Identify the most important constraint or limitation that's holding you back, and then focus on removing that limiting factor. It could be cash or staff or a new skill or habit you need or information for decision making. Whatever it is, identify it clearly and go to work to eliminate it.
6. **Step 6:** Once you've determined your goal, developed your plan, and identified your major obstacle, immediately take action of some kind toward achieving your goal. Step out in faith. Do the first thing that comes to mind. But do *something* to start moving toward your most important goal.
7. **Step 7:** Do at least one thing every day that moves you toward your most important goal. Make a habit of getting up each morning, planning your day and then doing something, anything, that moves you at least one step closer to what's most important to you.

Things to remember

- Do your research – are these the right goals?
- Be flexible – review, refine and reposition
- Measure your progress – reflect and review
- Ask for help – accountability often focuses the mind
- Be focused – you can't always multitask! Avoid distractions
- Block out your days – schedule 30 mins a day in your calendar
- Get good at managing your time

31

Slide 31 then provides some general advice about goal setting and planning;

- Keep reviewing your goals. - Are they still the right goals? Do they need to be flexed? How do you need to adapt, what will you do differently?
- Measure your progress – are the goals delivering what you need? Are you making enough progress? If not, what are the reasons behind this? What do you need to do differently?
- Do you find it easier to review goals on your own or with someone else? Would it help to be accountable to someone else?
- Block out time to focus on the goals – diary reminders, task schedule etc. Very tempting to skip but prioritise this or it will drop off the radar

Time management and prioritisation tool

	Urgent	Not Urgent
Important	Quadrant 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crisis • Pressing problems • Deadline driven projects 	Quadrant 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationship building • Finding new opportunities • Long-term planning • Preventive activities • Personal growth • Recreation
Not Important	Quadrant 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interruptions • Emails, calls, meetings • Popular activities • Proximate, pressing matters 	Quadrant 4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trivia, busy work • Time wasters • Some calls and emails • Pleasant activities

They will then be provided with a time management grid to help them to understand Urgent and important tasks. This assists prioritisation and how to become more effective. Usual practice is to focus on the urgent tasks- both important and not important. However, quadrant 2 is key, despite not being urgent some of the most important areas fall into here: Finding new opportunities, relationship building, planning, reviewing goals – also to look after yourself: Exercise, personal growth. These last one’s are crucial to keeping a person in a healthy state by keeping them in a state of physical and mental wellbeing.

There is then a selection of online planning tools (Slide 33) that will help people to prioritise their tasks and set themselves goals to complete. These can be useful for project goals involving others.

Other tools

Strides

Trello

Goals on track

Any Others?

2.6. Networking & Partnerships

Participants will have the topic introduced on slide 34 with an exercise on slide 35 asking ‘why are partnerships important?’. This question will be asked to the room and the answer’s will be flip charted before answers are provided on slide 36 to allow for any key gaps that have not been identified when the question is opened to the room.

Forming partnerships

As a small group- why are partnerships beneficial?

Why are partnerships beneficial

- New ideas, new opportunities
- Acquire new customers
- Increase revenues
- Expand geographical reach
- Find new markets
- Supply chains
- Raise finance
- New knowledge
- Collaboration opportunities
- Build brand awareness
- Share resources
- Filling skills gaps

How do you find partners?

What is networking and why is it important?

Everybody is relevant

“There are hundreds of people running around SXSW, Le Web, Web Summit and all those types of industry conferences who are the gateway to **your next big business move**. Because all it takes is **one personal connection. One great meeting**. It's not about the influence someone has; it's about **who they are and what they bring to the table.**”

37

Slide 36, poses the question ‘How do you find partners?’- the answer for this topic is networking- provided on slide 37 with the quote about networking.

Networking will begin to be introduced as a tool for finding partners on slide 37 and 38. Slide 37 is an optional slide on Networking – this highlights the importance of one personal connection. Finding the right personal connection.

Ask the group how they network currently – sector groups, membership groups, LinkedIn, twitter, Facebook, family and friends. This will prompt conversation and best practises to be discussed within the group. Trainers are to facilitate and guide this discussion re the benefits of networking and how to improve.

Networks: a route for spotting opportunity

- What is networking and why is it important
- Bridging and bonding

Slide 38 helps to emphasise this and the importance of one personal connection and finding the right personal connection. The group will be asked how the network currently- where through sector groups, membership groups, LinkedIn, twitter, Facebook and family and friends.

Entrepreneurs rely on social relationships not only for gaining access to information on entrepreneurial opportunities but also for mobilizing others to build new partnerships.

Social capital: An entrepreneur's ability to draw on resources from their social network which may include family, friends, business network, business forums social media. Social capital is an umbrella term including multiple relationships between entrepreneurs, their family, their community which is drawn on to bring resources to the business.

Need to build trust, partnerships don't happen overnight, and longer-term relationships will help unlock these opportunities.

Networking exercise

In groups with people you don't know-
max size of 4

Find out how you might benefit each
other if you were to partner up
10 minutes

39

People in small groups with others they don't know, maximum 4 per group, to find out how they might benefit each other if they were to partner up.

It is expected to take 10 minutes plus feedback to group.

Group members are numbered 1-4 and split into the four corners of the room. Try to split up those people that already know each other. Ask people to talk to as many people as possible in the group and find someone that could be useful for them in their current work and find out how you might benefit. You might need to speak to several people before you find a connection.

Reflection – Ask for feedback from individuals rather than the whole group to keep this exercise to time.

- What did you find useful?
- What did you find hard?
- What did you find easy?

Ask for feedback from individuals rather than the whole group to keep this exercise to time.

Networking hints and tips are shown on slide 40. These show simple tips to help beginners progress with networking, and to show those who may be more experienced something they may be missing. Depending on personality this is something that comes easier to some people than others. However, practice really helps. If this feels too intimidating start with smaller networking opportunities before moving onto larger events. Leverage social media. Follow up – don't use a standard LinkedIn follow up – remind the individual where you met them and what your shared interest is. See what they have learnt from the Networking exercise.

Networking hints and tips

- Prepare before you go
- Ask easy questions to open up the discussion
- Focus on the other person – learn what makes them think
- Smile
- Ditch the pitch
- Listen
- Share your passion
- Follow up – don't 'only connect' but do encourage engagement. Ask what kind of follow up they prefer
- Remember their name
- Don't be afraid to start a conversation – most people won't know many others and will welcome this

Slide 41 will then provide with networks that are across Europe and the web link so that they can tap into these and find out what they may offer.

Organisations that can support partnerships

2.7. Conclusions and homework

The key conclusion is that anybody can be an entrepreneur- they just need to think about their mindset and how they can alter and change this to become more entrepreneurial. To keep an open mind and seize opportunities. To set goals that meet the SMART targets and review them regularly. To network and find partnerships that work for you.

Slide 43 Internet resources- workshop participants are encouraged to read the provided material and watch the videos after the lecture to help them remember the material better.

Slide 44 provides resources and references that were used for attendees who would like to read more in depth about the area.

Slide 45 shows information about the next Merlin events specific to their area.

Slide 46 allows for reflection on the workshop. This lets the trainers collect information about what did and didn't work and what was the muddiest point.

Conclusions

- Anyone can be an entrepreneur- you need to think about your mindset
- Keep an open mind and seize opportunities
- Set your goals and review them regularly
- Network to find partnerships that work for you

Internet resources

Anyone can be and entrepreneur. All it takes is a little drive and ambition

Robert T. Kiyosaki

- Effectuation: <http://www.effectuation.org/>
- Peter Drucker: <https://hbr.org/2002/08/the-discipline-of-innovation>
- Enterprise Europe Network: <https://www.enterprise-europe.co.uk/>
- EBN: <https://ebn.eu/>
- Strides: <http://www.get2next.net/>

If you want to go deeper

Books

- Latham, G. P., & Locke, E. A. (1991). Self-regulation through goal setting. *Organizational behaviour and human decision processes*, 50(2), 212-247.
- Rich Baron, Tracey Milken, Doctor Isobah
- The Entrepreneurial Mindset: Strategies for Continuously Creating Opportunity in an Age of Uncertainty by Rita Gunther McGrath, Ian MacMillan
- Psychology of Entrepreneurship – Robert JR Baum, M Frese and R Baron ISBN 0-8058-5062-7
- Cantillon, R. 1952. Essai sur la nature du commerce en général. INED.
- Granovetter M (1983) The Strength of Weak Ties: A network Theory Revisited. Vol1 pp.201-223
- Katzner, I.M. 1973. Competition and entrepreneurship. University of Chicago press.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (1990). A theory of goal setting & task performance. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: US: Prentice-Hall.
- Sarasvathy S.D (2001) Causation and effectuation toward a theoretical shift from economic inevitability to entrepreneurial contingency
- Schumpeter, J.A. (1943). Capitalism, socialism and democracy. Routledge.
- Sarasvathy S.D. (2004) Making it happen: beyond theories of the firm to theories of firm design. Wiley on line library.

Information about next workshops

Year	Month	Event Name
2018	December	PPP Webinar
2018	22 nd November	Entrepreneurial Mindset
2019	January	Interpreting the Customer
2019	February	'Bring the Ideal' matchmaking session
2019	March	User Experience
2019	May	Lean Hardware
2019	June	Client matchmaking event
2019	July	Spinout vs Startup – differences, how to operate and succeed

Reflection

- What worked...
- What was useful...
- What wasn't relevant...
- How will you use the information learnt...

2.8. Assess your aptitude

This optional opportunity (GET2 test) may be of interest to participants to look at following the workshop. Get2 test offers an innovative way to test how entrepreneurial a person is and their strengths and weaknesses. It is offered as an extra to the participants if they want to do it. The trainers should have completed and printed off before the workshop to show their scores and to make the participants feel more at ease. It is not a tool to show why someone cannot be an entrepreneur, but a way of identifying a weakness that can be improved upon or skill gap that could be filled by another person.

<http://www.get2test.net/>

Assess your own aptitude

TEST YOUR ENTERPRISING POTENTIAL

If you want to be enterprising you are half-way there

TAKE GET2

<http://www.get2test.net>

 merlin
H2020 GA #780460

47

Finally slide 48 shows a closing slide for the workshop.

**DON'T BE LIMITED BY YOUR
MINDSET**

<https://merlin-ict.eu>

@Merlin_ICT

48

3. Building the Right IP For Your Business

3.1. General information about the workshop

Name of the workshop: Building the Right IP For Your Business

Name of the partner which is responsible for the content delivery: St John's Innovation Centre

Duration of the workshop: 4 hours

Optimal number of participants: from 20 to 30

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results and very early stage SMEs.

Target group needs identified: Understanding the differences between a start-up and a Spin-off, the need to importance of IP management for your idea and commercialisation journey, Understanding how to work constructively with a university when spinning out research.

Key skills to be acquired: Difference between a Start-Up and Spin-off, overview of IP, types of IP, processes for registering IP, working with universities and commercial partnerships.

The main goals of the workshop:

- Understand the key differences between operating a spin-off and a startup
- Understand how to work within local and university regulations to launch a spin-off
- Creating sustainable commercial partnerships
- Dealing with IPR issues such as patents and trademarks and licensing

Learning methods to be applied: Round table discussions, Q&A with IP experts, university tech transfer officers and both a start-up and spin-off

The main requirements for the venue: computer, projector, projector screen, whiteboard and able to seat 25-30 people.

Requirements for supplies needed: Pens, markers, large sheets of paper/flipchart, stopwatch or a phone with stopwatch, round table participants (TTO, Start-up, spin-off, IP Lawyer and facilitator).

3.2. Introduction to the workshop

The participants are first introduced first to the **workshop agenda**, which splits the Spin-off Start-up and IP into clear areas;

Then they are introduced to the learning objectives for the Spin-off vs Start-up workshop (as outlined in the grant agreement):

- Understand the key differences between operating a spin-off and a startup
- Understand how to work within local and university regulations to launch a spin-off
- Creating sustainable commercial partnerships
- Dealing with IPR issues such as patents and trademarks and licensing

The trainer will then introduce the rules/guidelines for the workshop, which include:

- No question is a silly question;
- What is said in the room stays in the room;
- Support and challenge each other.

The main purpose of the introduction of the rules for the workshop is to encourage the participants to ask questions, to reassure them that the questions asked will stay in the room, that information they share about their business/idea will stay in the room and everyone should support and challenge each other.

The general information about the workshop is provided:

- General housekeeping (toilets, fire-exits, food and drink)
- Length of the workshop (4 hours);
- Coffee break (20 minutes);
- Slides will be shared with the participants after the workshop- they are available via slide share.

The MERLIN project is presented briefly, introducing the goals of the project, events (other Workshops, webinars, international conferences to be planned). Furthermore, the main information about the Consortium partners is provided. This information is previously detailed in section 1. Introduction.

The participant will play 'the question game' as an Icebreaker to help to get the group interacting at the beginning of the workshop. Delegates will be split into groups of 5 people (if there is more than one representative from each organization they should be separated). A set of question cards have been prepared and will be distributed between the groups. Each person has 1 minute to answer each of the 5 questions on

a card and they will agree which answers they are going to feedback to the group after the exercise. We will hope to receive funny/poignant/off the wall answers to encourage interaction amongst the group.

The following sections of the document describe the content of each part in detail.

3.3. Difference between Start-ups and Spin-offs

The IP journey may differ depending on whether you are a Startup or Spin off business so important to understand the difference

First, we will define a start-up as ‘a newly emerged business venture that aims to meet a marketplace need, want or problem by developing a viable business model around products, services, processes or platforms. It should be noted that trainers are free to change this dependent on their favored definition or a definition they are happier to defend. Trainers should make it clear that there are is no agreed definition for start-ups. Other definitions include;

- Start-up is an early stage business who’s founder/s have come up with an idea for a product or service, researched the potential market, developed a business plan, raised funds and launched with the aim of rapid growth.
- A start-up is a new business venture designed to effectively develop and validate a scalable business model.
- Start-up is not the “child” of a university or its technology transfer office even if the founders come from a university and the university is a shareholder.

What is a Spin-Off

A spin-off company can be defined as a new, small, company formed to exploit IP developed during the course of an individual's employment in a larger organisation (e.g. a university).

H2020-GA #780460

11

Slide 11 has a slide defining a spin-off. The same applies as with Slide 10 that trainers are free to change this based on the definition that they are happiest to defend. The university will be the main shareholder initially and probably the assignor or licensor of the intellectual property going into the company. It may also initially exert a significant degree of organisational control until its shareholding and management role is diluted by successor investors.

Slide 12 contrasts both Spin-offs and Start-ups and links them together in a simplistic way:

All spin-offs are start-ups but not all start-ups are spin-offs

H2020-GA #780460

12

In general business terms: A **spin-off** is the creation of an independent **company** through the sale or distribution of new shares of an existing business or division of a parent. In the case of a University Spin-off the university is the parent company

A University **spin-off** is business entity formed in consultation with a tech transfer office at a university and the University and department involved to commercialise IP developed through university research. It is likely to have university investment, shared IP and probably university staff.

What's the difference? Exercise (15 mins)

Slide 13 is an exercise to ask participants to think about the differences between start-ups and spin-offs. The group will be split into groups of 3-4, with 15 minutes and then 15 minutes feedback to the group. Will be asked how they are constructed/formed, operated, developed, financed? What are the good things/bad things? Answers will be flip-charted during the feedback. Slides 14-16 will show the differences between start-ups and spin-offs to see whether the answers brought up by the group are the same as the ones brought up by the group.

Compare and contrast (1)

Spin-off

- Origin – takes place within the academic/research institution
- University IP ownership stake
- University is a shareholder - shared equity arrangements
- Impact – may be social as well as financial

Start-up

- Origin – outside the academic/research institution
- IP is self-owned for company benefit
- Owned by founders
- Shareholder agreement between founders. Equity agreed by founders and negotiated with any investors

Compare and contrast (2)

Spin-off

- May allow flexible roles
- University contribution to IP costs
- Support with initial costs and introductions to investors (sometimes!)
- Ongoing support with commercialisation – access to specialists i.e. IP, legal
- Access to facilities – lab space plus technical input
- Access to University support programmes e.g. iCure in UK
- May find potential commercial partners

Start-up

- Likely to be full time in the business
- IP and initial costs usually self financed or via fundraising -friends and family, grants, investment
- Need to find ongoing support and ensure sufficient resources to cover costs
- Need to find own premises and source specialist equipment
- Need to source own commercial partners and any ongoing support requirements

Compare and contrast (3)

Spin-off

- Process of agreeing Spin off with parent may be lengthy, bureaucratic and lacking in flexibility
- Possible obligation to include university employees in team
- Exit- University will be looking for a planned exit within agreed timescales. Often seeking early returns
- You might not get the terms you want

Start-up

- Can progress more quickly without bureaucracy/decision making by others outside the business
- Founders choose and build the team
- Exit is at the discretion of the founders and any investors
- The Board is in control

Slide 17 and 18 are prospective journeys of spin-offs and start-ups to help illustrate the different routes the companies may take.

Start-up: A possible journey

This is a flexible and bare model. Several activities can be implemented concurrently or in varying orders. Note this is one version only and there will be lots of different options and no fixed order

Obviously, product development, evaluation, manufacture and commercialisation may require the involvement of third parties such as designers, R&D collaboration partners, licensors, licensees, agents and distributors. Contracts will need entering into with all such parties.

Spin-off: A possible journey

Again – this may play out differently depending on a number of factors, parent organisation, sector etc. Note this is one version only and there will be lots of different options and no fixed order

Again, third party involvement will be inevitable.

In taking on investors the company will be getting money and (with luck) valuable contacts and expertise but needs to be aware that:

1. Founders' shareholdings may get diluted and, as the company grows, they may get ousted or marginalised.
2. Investors' preferential rights could leave the founders (and the university) with little return when the company gets sold.

Spin-off case study: Ziylo

Ziylo- Co-founded by Bristol University student Dr Harry Destecroix. Harry co-founded Ziylo when studying for his PhD 4 years ago at the University of Bristol. They created technology that can be developed to treat diabetes more effectively. The initial IP was discovered and Ziylo was founded to develop the molecule. Other directors of Ziylo include the primary investor, Keith Macdonald and the Dr Andrew Chapman, who also led the development of this science.

They began producing glucose responsive insulins (GRIs)- the “holy grail” of insulin which Destecroix said he hoped the sale would offer ground-breaking treatment for diabetics. They produced a synthetic molecule which works by binding glucose in the bloodstream more effectively. The molecule is a product of 20 years work at the Anthony Davis Lab at the university.

Norvo Nordisk purchased the company for a figure of up to £623m (\$800m) dependent on the success of the molecule. They aim to develop a new type of insulin which aims to help diabetics manage their condition more safely. The acquisition gives Novo Nordisk full rights to Ziylo’s glucose binding molecule platform to develop glucose responsive insulins (GRIs). The development of this technology is a key strategic area for Novo Nordisk in its effort to develop this next generation of insulin, which would lead to a safer and more effective insulin therapy. A GRI could also lead to better metabolic control and therefore reduce the overall burden of diabetes for people living with the disease.

The glucose binding molecules discovered have the potential to lead to the development of insulins, which could remove the risk of hypoglycaemia.

The initial IP was discovered and Ziylo was founded to develop the molecule.

This is an astounding achievement by Ziylo and we are delighted for Harry and the team. It is a great demonstration of how you can take an idea or a concept and transfer it into a commercial reality through the incubation route.

Spin-off case study: Ziylo

To contrast this there is the case-study of Raspberry Pi for an example of a Start-up that was from researchers but was not a Spin-off as the IP was not developed within a university.

Raspberry Pi is a Credit-card sized device and one of the lowest-cost computers available. At first glance it looks nothing like what is generally considered a computer but is capable. Steve Furber- PhD from Cambridge. Looked into building cheap computers. Went to work for Broadcom. When designing his cheap computers, he showed them a prototype, enough people liked what he had made and what they saw. MIT were going to make a clone of the apple 2 and make a low-cost computer. After email conversations to re-do the BBC micro. Then a group settled on making a small high-powered low-cost computer. Had a prototype on a Broadcom chip. They wanted to build something that would get kids into coding having seen a decline in people coming into computer science and computing among kids. There was a decline in students arriving to study computer science with experience of coding. It turned out the best way to do this was to combine his previous experience to build a low-cost chip/computer that was cheap enough for them to buy and easy enough for them to hack. Was run with University professors and staff that had also noticed this trend. Made a Cambridge designed broadcom chip with and ARM 11 in. They were nervous to show this to kids for the first time as they did not know the response they would get- but they took them into a school and children went crazy for them.

Raspberry Pi had a number of influential people and trustees however had very modest resources. They did not have enough money to build them at a high enough rate so to meet the demand struck a deal with major electronics distributors Premier Farnell and RS components and licensed them to manufacture and distribute the boards. They were made originally in china but from September last year some was moved to wales sony factory.

The early adopters of the Pi where typically adults who had found a cool new toy to hack and already had an invested interest in programming and computer science, grown-up adults accounted for 4/5 of the sales. However, there is a shift occurring towards younger children with sales, as parents, teachers and children have all picked up the device- as well as an estimated hundreds of schools.

10,000 boards they had made sold out on the 1st day with 100,000 chips bought on the first day. As of March 2017, Raspberry Pi announced they had become the bestselling British made computer and the 3rd best selling all-purpose computer worldwide hitting the milestone of 12.5 million sold worldwide.

Do not believe they could have run this project anywhere but Cambridge (Outside of the bay area/Silicon Valley)- the mix of people for technology and innovation- Broadcom based, arm based. People at Broadcom doing work in their work at evenings and weekends.

Start Up Case Study – Raspberry Pi

3.4. Intellectual property- IP

Intellectual Property- IP

St Johns has consulted an international IP firm, Marks and Clerk LLP, to help with the content generation for this workshop to ensure clarity with regulations. We will be producing a podcast/teaching material to be disseminated amongst partners to help with the understanding and to keep long lasting resource for the project.

The section will outline the different types of IP, how to search for existing IP and a patent exercise.

IP - is it really necessary? Yes! Why?

What is IP? Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce*

You do not need IP to commercialise products

- IP is **not** a right to practice an invention
- Obtaining IP will not guarantee commercial success

But...IP can be:

- A weapon or bargaining tool
- A source of revenue

*[Source: World Intellectual Property Office (WIPO)]

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

22

IP can be technical or artistic, e.g., for technical inventions (patents, know-how) or to protect branding (designs, trademarks, copyright)

Clarify a common misunderstanding: an IP registration is not an authorisation or confirmation that you are free to use the IP (e.g. practice an invention). It is a means to *potentially* block others from using that IP.

- **Weapon:** IP may in certain circumstances be used as a 'weapon' to actively block a 3rd party entering your market. But be careful not to "threaten" 3rd parties – speak with an IP solicitor first!
- **Revenue:** IP may be a deterrent to others wishing to enter your market or convince them to pay for a license rather than risk infringement proceedings at court. Depending on your business model, you may wish to license your IP to obtain revenue, and/or profit from commercially offering your own products/services using that IP.

IP – is it worth it?

Often cited figure: IP can constitute up to 80% of a company's value

- Coca-Cola - Brand worth \$80.31 billion in 2016
- Black and Decker Workmate – independent inventor patented product – licensed on over 30 million units worldwide
- Ketchup bottle valve (patented) – company sold for \$13 million in 1995
- iPhone (design) – nearly \$400 million in damages against Samsung (now under review)

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

23

Would any of these products become household names without IP protection?

- Coca-Cola – infamous “secret recipe” (know-how); no other fizzy pops tastes the same.
- Black and Decker (B&D) Workmate – invented at home by Ron Hickman (Director of Engineering for Lotus). Hickman filed patents, designs and Workmate® trademark. B&D initially rejected the concept; Stanley said sales would be Stanley “in dozens rather than hundreds”. B&D changed their minds after Hickman made and sold 14,000. Since then, >100 million, reputedly with a royalty to Ron Hickman for each, have been sold.
- Ketchup upside-down bottle: invented by Paul Brown in 1991 (borrowed from friends and family for 111 prototypes), patent initially licensed to NASA, Heinz and shampoo manufacturers, in 1995 sold his company and IP rights for \$14M.
- iPhone: more recently - California jury 2018: \$539M re design and utility patents for e.g. rounded corners, the rim of the front face of the iPhone, and the app grid layout of iOS home screen

Different IP rights

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

24

Slide 24 shows some concepts may be protected by multiple types of IP, e.g.; Trademarks, designs and copyright for branding-related concepts; Designs and Patents for physical construction of products.

It is important to detail the different types of IP

Unregistered IP:

Copyright – literally blocks 3rd parties from any (unlicensed) right to copy another person’s original artistic work, e.g., text, drawings, sculptures, etc.

- Designs – non-technical aspects of physical appearance. Unregistered design rights arise automatically but must prove direct copying – this is difficult. Registered Designs more effective.
- Confidential Information - trade secrets may be, e.g., sales databases, inventions or technical know-how protected by secrecy rather than patents (note obvious risk) know-how typically arises from an individual’s accumulated experience and may /may not be understood or patentable. Trade secrets can be vital, e.g., Coca Cola recipe. Most inventions start off as trade secrets which provides short-term protection prior to the marketing of your invention. Inventors are often initially cautious about revealing their inventions to others. Trade secret protection is not appropriate for the long-term protection of any ideas which can be readily ascertained by reverse engineering or for inventions that can be independently created.
- Passing off rights – “misrepresentation” to unfairly benefit from another company’s goodwill/reputation in the market - generally one company markets products with similar branding to another company’s, thus confusing customers regarding the origin of the goods or services

Emphasise the need to document all unregistered IP, keep a secure record, have someone in the organisation responsible for keeping and updating records, have a review process.

(GUI- Graphical User Interface)

Registered IP: You do not need to prove active copying in order to show that a 3rd party is infringing your IP.

- Patents – technical inventions, usually (but not always) created by engineers/scientists, including sometimes software engineers.
- Designs – non-technical aspects of physical appearance. (GUI- Graphical User Interface)
- Trademarks – indicates origin of goods.

Unregistered IP

- Unregistered IP**
- Copyright** – expression of an idea (art, literature, software source code, GUI)
 - Database rights** (separate to copyright)
 - Designs** – appearance/shape/configuration
 - Confidential information** (trade secrets, eg know-how - is it documented?)
 - Passing off rights** acquired from use (trading)
 - Others** (domain names, topologies, SPCs...)

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

Registered IP

Registered IP

Patents - the technical idea underlying a product/process

Designs – visual appearance, including GUIs

Trade marks – a badge of origin

Copyright – what does it protect?

- Books, technical reports, manuals, databases
- Engineering, technical or architectural plans
- Paintings, sculptures, photographs
- Music, songs, plays, dramatic works
- Promotional literature, advertising
- Films, videos, cable or radio broadcasts
- Computer software

Copyright is a legal term describing **rights given to creators** for their literary and artistic works.

The purpose of copyright is to allow creators to gain economic rewards for their efforts and so encourage future creativity and the development of new Copyright material is usually the result of creative skill and significant work and investment, and without protection, it would often be very easy for others to exploit material without paying the creator.

- Intellectual creation expressing the authors personality

- Author owns – covers both published and unpublished works

Copyright holder can grant permission or licence anyone else to use these without affecting ownership of the actual copyright of their work e.g. author may permit a tv adaptation of their work.

- Copyright is an automatic right. No steps needed to acquire protection (no fee – free) However, most countries have a system in place to allow for the voluntary registration of works. Such voluntary registration systems can help solve disputes over ownership or creation, as well as facilitate financial transactions, sales, and the assignment and/or transfer of rights.
- An employer usually owns the copyright in a work produced by an employee in the course of employment. However, a contractor will usually retain copyright unless their contract states otherwise.
- How long does it last? Life time of author plus 70 years

The law provides certain ways in which copyright works may be used without the need to first obtain permission from the copyright holder eg fair use (to make copies), public domain, library privilege, copying for examinations and copying for instruction.

Trademarks

- Any sign which is capable of being represented graphically
- Any sign which is capable of distinguishing the goods or services of one undertaking from another

A Badge of Origin

A trademark is anything by which customers can identify a product or the source of a product, such as a name associated with the product. Typically, that would be the graphics or words that you use to refer to your product or service. When the brand or trademark is made up of words, it is referred to as a wordmark.

- Capable of being graphically represented and Capable of distinguishing
- Classification – 45 different classes of goods and services

-
- If goods/service are incorrectly classified, the validity of the registered mark's right may be called into question at a later date.

All the value of a brand – its philosophy, its values, its know-how, its staff, its products, its intangible assets – is encapsulated in one symbol: its trade mark. Trade marks capture the essence of brands and the energy, investment and know-how that goes into them. If you're serious about your brand, you must develop your own trade mark. Your brand is part of your value – ie Apple. It grew through the protection and development of its intellectual property: the trade marks, designs, copyright and patents.

Trademark registration will confer an exclusive right to the use of the registered trademark. This implies that the trademark can be exclusively used by its owner or licensed to another party for use in return for payment. Registration provides legal certainty and reinforces the position of the right holder, for example, in case of litigation.

A trade mark must be unique. Participants should understand what trademarks can include:

- Words
- Sounds
- Logos
- Colours
- A combination of any of the above.

Participants must understand that Trademarks do not cover:

- Be offensive- No swear words or pornography
- Describe the goods or services it will relate to – for example the word 'silk ' cannot be a trade mark for a silk textile company
- Be misleading. For example, use the word organic when it is not
- Be a 3 D shape associated with your trade mark. E.g. take the shape of an egg for eggs
- Be non-distinctive. For example – we lead the way
- Look like similar state symbols like flags or hall marks

This section can be run as an exercise to see what participants know about what participants know they do or don't cover before viewing the slides.

How to register a Trademark

33

This section is focusing on how to register a trademark, and explaining the difference between regional, nation and international registration. If you want protection in more Member States of the EU, you can apply for an EU trade mark from EU IPO – this is the European route. An online application at EUIPO costs €850 and is filed in one language. The EU IOP will check your application when received, and once registered, your trade mark can be renewed indefinitely every 10 years.

At the international level, you have two options: either you can file a trademark application with the trademark office of each country in which you are seeking protection, or you can use WIPO’s Madrid System. Madrid – The International Trademark System

The Madrid System is a convenient and cost-effective solution for registering and managing trademarks worldwide. File a single application and pay one set of fees to apply for protection in up to 118 countries. Modify, renew or expand your global trademark portfolio through one centralized system.

Must do a search before registering <https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en/search-availability>

Links to organisations will be included at end of presentation

Registered Designs

Protects shape or configuration (**3-D**) and/or pattern or ornamentation (2-D)

No protection for function, materials or technology of manufacture

No protection when form is dictated by function (ie: *no design freedom*)

34

This section focuses on helping participants to understand registered designs and the process for registration. The appearance of the whole or part of a product resulting from the features of the lines, contours, colours, shape, texture or materials of the product or its ornamentation (shape or configuration).

A registered Community design (RCD) grants you exclusive rights in all current and future Member States of the European Union through a single registration, filed online. It is valid for 5 years and it can be renewed for a maximum of 25 years, 5 years at a time.

If you do business in a single EU country, you may want to register your design there. You'll have the exclusive right to it within the country of your choice, but you won't be able to prevent anyone from copying it in other EU countries. If you do business in more than one EU country, you should consider the option of obtaining a design right that is valid throughout the entire EU: a registered Community design (RCD). The RCD is an all-or-nothing deal: either you get it for all or you do not get it at all.

RCD advantages:

Practical advantages to the RCD;

- RCDs are governed by a single legal system, providing strong and uniform protection throughout the European Union.
- An RCD is easy to register. There is one application, one language of filing and one file to manage.
- RCD registration offers the possibility to file multiple applications (i.e. to include several designs in one application, such as variations of the same design).

Financial advantages;

- The fee for registering and publishing one design is €350 for five years' protection.

- An RCD saves you translation and administrative costs.
- The design system offers a 'bulk discount'. For a multiple application, the fees for registering the 2nd to the 10th design are subject to a 50% discount while, for the 11th design onwards, the fee is just 25% that of the basic fee per design.
- Fee £50 UK ONLY – each partner to check prices in their country.
- Lasts for 25 years
- Renewal fee paid every 5 years (incrementally expensive)

How to register a Design

35

Design right that is valid throughout the entire EU: a registered Community design (RCD). The RCD is an all-or-nothing deal: either you get it for all or you do not get it at all. This slide articulates the process for registering a design.

Searches for existing IP

36

We want to ensure participants are well informed on how to search for existing IP prior to registration. eSearch +is EUIPO's access to its database of European Union trademarks and registered Community designs. It can help you find out if someone has registered a similar trade mark with us. With eSearch plus, you can also perform image searches and image monitoring, find a representative, or search the Bulletin.

The [TMview database](#) contains information from all of the EU national IP offices, the European Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) and a number of international partner offices outside the EU on trade mark applications and registered marks. A trade mark applied for or registered at national level before yours could pose a threat to your application.

Links are also available at the end of the presentation.

Patents

Protection for a technical invention:

- Product, process, apparatus
- how things work
- what they do
- how they do it
- what they are made of
- how they are made

Most patents are for incremental improvements in known technology – evolution rather than revolution

- The invention must be **new**, **inventive** and **industrially applicable**
- First English patent granted by Henry VI in 1449 - method of making stained glass.

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

37

This section is to develop participants understanding of patents and the process of generating a patent. Patents are a government authority or licence conferring a right or title for a set period giving the sole right to exclude others from making, using or selling an invention. They must be;

- New and previously undisclosed
- Distinguished by an inventive step not obvious to someone expert in that technology
- Capable of industrial application
- Lasts for 20 years
- Renewal (4th anniversary from file then annual fee)

Things you cannot (at least in the UK) patent “as such” are, e.g. (please note there is expected to be local changes dependent on changes across Europe in what cannot be used for a patent:

- discoveries, scientific theories and mathematical methods;
- aesthetic creations;
- schemes, rules and methods for performing mental acts, playing games or doing business, and programs for computers;
- presentations of information.

But these are narrow exceptions. For example, software inventions are patentable if they have technical character, e.g., by controlling a physical apparatus/process or improving performance (e.g., speed) of a computer.

Common misunderstanding: potential commercial value of an invention is not a direct indicator of patentability. A direct indicator is whether an invention is new and not obvious (i.e., inventive) to a person having ‘ordinary’ technical skill, e.g., lab technician.

("Industrially applicable" generally means that the invention can be used in the real world – this requirement should be simple to comply with!)

Slides 38-41 will have a patent quiz where participants can gain an understanding of the scope of patents and what they encompass. 2 examples are given on slides 38 and 40 with the answers on slides 39 and 41 respectively.

Example Patent Claim – Quiz 1

Which stationary item is covered by the following claim:

A sheet metal binder clip having
extremities maintained in juxtaposition by the resiliency of the metal,
handle receiving and operating jaws formed at said extremities and
comprising separated, oppositely disposed duplex cam surfaces and
handles having opposite ends journaled in said jaws and operating against said cam
surfaces.

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

Trainers will put this slide up and ask the group to guess what is being described. The learnings generated need to be around the specific use of language even for the simplest of objects and that professional input will be required.

What is a Patent? Quiz 1 - Answer

US1,139,627

Example Patent Claim – Quiz 2

1. A system for **engaging shoes with a hitch means to permit a person standing on a stage surface to lean forwardly beyond his or her center of gravity**, comprising:

at least one shoe having a heel with a first engagement means, said first engagement means comprising a recess formed in a heel of said shoe covered with a heel slot plane located at a bottom region of said heel, said heel slot plane having a slot formed therein with a relatively wide opening at a leading edge of said heel and a narrower terminal end rearward of said leading edge, said recess being larger in size above said terminal end of said slot than is said terminal end of said slot; and

a second engagement means, detachably engageable with said first engagement means, comprising a hitch member having an enlarged head portion connected by a narrower shank portion to a means for raising and lowering said head of said hitch member above and substantially level with or below said stage surface, said head portion being larger in size than said terminal end of said slot and said shank portion being narrower than said terminal end of said slot, wherein said hitch member can be moved through apertures in said stage surface between a projecting position raised above said stage surface and a retracted position at or below the stage surface, and when said head portion of said hitch member is raised above said stage surface, **said first engagement means can be detachably engaged with said projecting hitch member, thereby allowing a person wearing the shoes to lean forwardly with his or her normal center of gravity beyond a front region of said shoes, and maintain said forward lean.**

What is a Patent? Quiz 2 - Answer

United States Patent [19]
Jackson et al.

US9852542A
 [11] Patent Number: **5,255,452**
 [4] Date of Patent: **Oct. 26, 1993**

[54] **METHOD AND MEANS FOR CREATING ANTI-GRAVITY ILLUSION**

[71] Inventors: **Michael J. Jackson, Los Angeles, Michael L. Bush, Dennis Tompkins, both of Hollywood, Calif.**

[72] Assignee: **Tough International, Inc., Los Angeles, Calif.**

[21] Appl. No.: **956,879**

[22] Filed: **Jun. 29, 1992**

[31] Int. Cl.⁷: **A43B 5/00; A43B 5/02**

[32] U.S. Cl.: **36/136; 36/70; 36/122; 36/1, 93, 105, 111, 36/134, 131, 132, 136; 482/70, 71, 95**

[56] **References Cited**
 U.S. PATENT DOCUMENTS
 1,099,284 4/1913 Denny 36/114
 2,124,796 4/1938 Venable 36/122
 2,475,399 4/1949 Meach 36/1

3,899,391 6/1975 Smith 36/1
 4,045,237 9/1980 Gowan 36/114
 4,174,680 9/1980 Tinsley 36/111
 4,345,466 2/1981 Ellis 36/112
 4,762,819 9/1988 Best 36/111
 4,882,819 11/1989 Sargent 36/111
 5,082,771 9/1990 Blumfeld 36/113

Primary Examiner—Steven N. Meyers
Assistant Examiner—M. Denise Peterson
 Attorney, Agent, or Firm—Cruicker & Simmons

ABSTRACT
 A system for allowing a shoe wearer to lean forwardly beyond his center of gravity by virtue of wearing a specially designed pair of shoes which will engage with a black member axially projectable through a heel surface. The shoes have a specially designed heel dot which can be detachably engaged with the black member by simply tilting the shoe wearer's feet forward, thereby engaging with the black member.

13 Claims, 4 Drawing Sheets

H2020 GA #780460

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

The “claims” of a patent (generally speaking, not the detailed description or drawings) define the scope of potential protection. Claims use specialist legal language. Generally, a skilled patent attorney will be needed to draft new claims, argue patentability of the claims (e.g., relative to prior art, or the legal exceptions to patentability), and to analyse Freedom to Operate relative to 3rd party patent claims. The answer for the first example is a bulldog clip.

Patents don’t need to be for e.g., mass manufactured goods or scientific laboratory equipment. The main requirements are that the inventions are technical, new and inventive.

Even Michael Jackson invented his own product and was awarded a patent! How did this IP and technology affect his success?

This is designed to be a fun exercise to be run with a small group to help them to guess what the innovation might look like from the description given.

How to spot an opportunity

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

Slide 42 is to help participants to understand when and when not to file application for a patent. Filing an application can quickly lead to a high-quality search report. The relevant cited prior art (if any) will help you to decide if the costs of other patent applications, e.g., direct foreign applications and/or a PCT application, may be worthwhile.

Assuming the UK application is the first filing of your invention, any further application must be submitted within 12months of your UK filing date (i.e., with the ‘priority period’ according to the Paris Convention). Some detail will be given on indicative costs and timelines for securing a patent.

As the participants may be entering this at an entry level, we have included optional slides throughout, slide 43: Patents – National Rights is one of these. It has increased depth that depending on the level of the existing knowledge of the audience on the day of the workshop can be changed.

Patents – National Rights

- Patents are national rights
- A separate patent must be obtained in each country of interest. A UK patent will only protect in the UK – if foreign protection is required then you have to file abroad
- There are no international patents, only international patent *applications*. Various conventions and treaties aim to ease routes to foreign protection:

EPC provides a procedure leading to a bundle of national patents

PCT allows delayed applications for national patent applications

UPC may in future allow "European Patents", but only if ratified across Europe...

- Up to 20 years from filing
 - Can take a long time to get granted (3-5 years) but can be quicker
 - Once granted renewal fees must be paid to keep in force

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

43

EPC: European Patent Convention – European Patent Office (EPO) grants a patent application that is then converted into individual patents for respective European countries. Nb the EPC is not related to the European Union.

PCT: Patent Cooperation Treaty – filing a single (i.e., minimal cost) PCT application secures the opportunity, but delays the deadline, for requesting patents at different national offices around the world. This delay usually means you have more certainty regarding the commercial value of your patent application, by the time the deadline for incurring the costs of applications in multiple countries (US, CN, EP, JP etc) arrives. Most countries are PCT members (few exceptions eg Argentina, Iraq, Pakistan).

UPC: Unitary Patent Court – not yet in force, pending resolution of constitutional complaint in Germany. If comes into force, the EPO will then be able to grant a "European Patent" covering many European countries (i.e., not requiring conversion into individual patents for respective countries).

Patent term - generally 20yrs from the filing date regardless of time to grant. (Shorter terms for 'petty' (utility) patents, e.g., German Gebrauchsmuster). You cannot enforce a patent (i.e., sue a third party for infringement) until it is granted.

3.5. Working within university and other regulations & Creating Sustainable partnerships

We want researchers to understand the need to discuss with their tech transfer office's prior to progressing any IP registration.

Every University has their own IP policy and employment contract that varies by university let alone by country. So giving an overview of what researchers should be checking is important to equip them with the relevant checklist to be able to find out how they can work.

Working within local and University regulations

What does your contract with the University say? Who owns the IP?

What does the University's IP policy say?

Involve the Technology Transfer Office from the start

Take your own legal advice if you think the University doesn't own the IP before walking off with it

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

45

Check your employment contract – do you own the IP? Does the university? Has a third party supplied grant funding with conditions attached? If your employment contract is silent on the issue check the University IP policy and associated documentation.

Have the conversation with TTO early- this will allow you to understand the situation from the beginning and have open conversations with them. BUT don't disclose the idea to anyone before then as you may ruin the chances of patentability. Check and double check regulations and understand the process! Finally make sure to ask questions. This will provide researchers and University staff to understand whether they own the IP and what the options are re spinning out or starting up.

It is important that there is not only an understanding of IP but the other parts of the process that can go wrong. The other workshops in this series will have help with the understanding of parts of this (i.e. commercial aspects- finding customers, lean start-up, user experience etc.). But some that are more specific when coming from a research background;

Lots of things, actually

What could go wrong?!

- IP Ownership
- Commercial
- Administrative
- Regulatory
- Personal
- Contractual

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

47

We want participants to be prepared for what might go wrong and how best to reduce these risks. In many cases the technology is patentable, but the company fails for other reasons. Often, one can tell early on that this is going to happen.

If the founders fall out (e.g. over who will be in charge, who will be a director or how shares will be distributed) they may soon start sending their advisors conflicting instructions behind each other's backs and the company will fall apart.

PhD supervisors often demand a directorship, shares and to be named on the patent as an inventor even if their contribution was minimal.

One of the most important influencers of success is the people behind and idea. It is really important that you have the right team on board for commercialisation. This may not necessarily be the same people that have got your business to the current stage. You need to be gearing up around business development, possibly fundraising, sales and marketing. Should you be seeking the advice of someone that has been there/done it- A mentor. Understand where the gaps in your team are, do you have the right people on your board?

Do you have the right people?

- Do they get on with each other? Do they get on with outsiders?
- Are they experienced? Is their experience the right kind?
 - Do you need mentors?
- Is anyone missing?
 - Experienced CEO
 - Marketing person from the right sector
Remember, needn't be employed full-time
- Is anyone superfluous?
 - The CEO's best mate
 - The PhD supervisor who didn't actually do anything

The technology is oh, so, fascinating BUT:

- Is it already out there?
- Would anyone want it anyway?
- Might someone beat you to it?
- Might it just bomb even if it's good?
- Are you the ones who should be selling it anyway? Do you need:

New Staff?

Agents?

Distributors

Companies should do some market research before deciding to develop their product. See search links provided at end of presentation. New staff that start-ups most commonly need are a CFO and a marketing/business development person with experience in the company's specific market sector. Agents get customers for you and you sell to those customers and pay the agent a commission. Distributors buy your products and resell them into the market in their own name.

Good Housekeeping

Keep up to date records of:

- Inventions
- IP portfolio
- Know-how
- Contracts
- Confidential information disclosed and received
- Excel spreadsheets with summaries are a good idea
- Diarise key dates

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

This section of the workshop will help participant understand the importance of good IP housekeeping. Act from day one like you're going to sell the company because, even if you don't, running it will be much easier. Good house-keeping makes due-diligence much more bearable if you sell the company or get investment? Absolutely essential to securing your IP – IP Management Strategy

Know the regulatory and legal framework

Generally;

- Company law
- Directors' duties
- Data protection
- Freedom of information
- Trading and advertising standards

For your sector;

- Industry Standards
- GCP
- GLP
- GMP
- Patent consent and confidentiality

Do you need insurance?

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

Make sure you use an insurance broker specializing in your product/technology field because:

1. They will give you useful advice in how to be a “good risk”.
2. They will have a better chance of getting you the best cover for the best premium.

You will be entering into contracts such as:

- IP assignments and licences in
- Confidentiality agreements
- Materials transfer agreements
- Employment and director's service agreements
- Consultancy agreements
- R&D Collaborations
- Licences out
- Agency and distribution agreements
- Standard terms of purchase and supply

© 2018 Marks & Clerk LLP | Marks & Clerk is a registered trade mark.

52

Slide 52 focuses on collaboration and what to consider before embarking on a collaborative deal. This list roughly follows the life cycle of a company from technology inception to product launch.

Think about your processes and procedures, roles and responsibilities – training requirements. If spinning out use your University tech transfer team for support.

If you enter in to a contract be 100% your company can perform it. Be happy the other side can – suing them for breach of contract is not a good outcome. Don't sign a really bad contract just to land that customer/supplier/licensor/licensee. Even if the other side is much bigger than you, the contract is likely to be negotiable up to a point. Bad contracts deter potential buyers and investors. Reputational risk

Contracts – Common pitfalls

- There is no contract
- It's written on the back of a fag packet
- It makes no sense or is vaguely drafted
- It bears no relation to reality
- Not all stakeholders know about it
- It is hideously one-sided
- It contains illegal or unenforceable provisions
- It is subject to foreign law and jurisdiction

Why you may not actually own “your” IP

- Inventors never assigned rights into company
- Consultant still owns IP
- Inadequate wording - "X will assign to Y"
- Co-owners you didn't know about
- Other parties with rights e.g. grantors

This section outlines common pitfalls. Inventors often forget to assign the IP into the company when they set it up. If employees generate IP for a company in the course of their employment the company automatically owns the IP. This is not the case with consultants and contractors – you need an express assignment from them. “X will assign to Y” is merely a statement of intent. You will need an operative assignment from X to Y. If you received a grant check IP ownership around this, particularly if part of a collaborative project.

To continue engagement from the group an exercise will be run on the pros and cons with dealing with big companies. This will be open to the room to flipchart the answers before they are shown on the following slide.

Dealing with big companies?

What are the Pros and Cons?
5 mins in small groups

Pros and cons of dealing with big companies?

This section is designed to be interactive and will draw on any previous experience in the room. Outline below are example pros and cons

- Expertise – wide pool of skills to draw on can lead to improved innovation. Can present significant opportunities for growth
- Decision-making may be slow as a big company may need several people to say yes and they aren't often in the same room at the same time.
- Payment may be slow because big companies' accounts departments have lots of transactions to process. Sometimes they take their time paying because the company owed money is small and they think they can get away with it.
- Big companies impose limited budgets on teams and departments too so big companies aren't just bottomless bags of cash.
- If a big company undergoes a change in ownership or direction or a new team leader takes over the project, your technology/product may be dropped, and it may have nothing to do with the merit of your offering.

As agreed with the guest speakers who helped to produce the content for the slides their information will be shown at the end of the deck. This will allow for direction to contacts that have strong knowledge in this area.

The next section will help to bring the content to life for participants by having a presentation from both a spin-off and a start-up about their journey to commercialisation and how they have maximised the value of their IP for their businesses.

Guest Speaker - Corrosion Radar

Partners will each select a spin off company of their choice to talk about. Making this relevant to the local audiences will be important.

Guest Speaker - Camnexus

camnexus

59

Partners will each select a start-up company of their choice to talk about. Making this relevant to the local audiences will be important.

3.6. Round table Q&A

Round-Table Q&A

A large part of this workshop will be the bringing in expertise on this topic to answer questions from the group.

The latter part of the workshop will be a round table discussion with companies/professionals on this top.

This slide should be populated with representative's logos from their organization.

Here are some suggestions of roles from the following disciplines you may want to include:

- Intellectual Property Lawyer
- A successful Spin-off (could be the same person that gives a case study)
- A successful start up
- Tech transfer officer
- Corporate collaborator - optional

The group needs to have a facilitator who would manage the Q and A process. We expect this section to last at least an hour.

3.7. Conclusions and homework

If you want to go deeper

Useful Links

- <https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en> Intellectual Property Office for Europe
- <http://www.wipo.int/portal/en/index.html> - World Intellectual Property Organisation
- <https://www.eucopyright.com/>
- <https://euipo.europa.eu/ohimportal/en/image-search-design>
- <https://www.tmdn.org/tmdsview-web/welcome> Design View Centralized access point to view the registered design information held by any of the participating National Offices,
- <https://www.gov.uk/search-registered-design> - Find a registered design in UK
- <https://euipo.europa.eu/eSearch/> Search trademarks, designs, owners in the EU
- <https://www.tmdn.org/tmview/welcome> - Trademark database plus details for national offices
- <https://www.epo.org/applying/basics.html> Applying for a European patent
- <https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/technical/espacenet.html#tab=1> Patent search tool

61

Those participants who want to go deeper into the topic can read the articles and books provided. These readings offer more information on the topic on a deeper level.

Information about next workshops in XYZ

62

This slide will give partners the opportunity to populate specifically for their areas outlining the future project activities. To be updated nearer the time once dates/venues confirmed.

4. Conclusions

Both workshops – Entrepreneurial Mindset and Building the Right IP For Your Business – aim to equip researchers with skills and tools that help them successfully commercialize their research findings and bridge the gap between science findings and business.

Both workshops provide the participants with powerful tools and knowledge that have been proven useful and successful in real life applications. This will enable them to think more creatively, network and plan more constructively, understand the different types of IP and the relevance to their commercialisation. Workshop 8 will also offer the opportunity for participants to have follow-up discussions and a 1-to-1 basis with an IP lawyer.